

Possible Transmission Route for IAPP and Amyloid Cell-Cell Transfer

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Popular Scientific Summary

In type 2 diabetes, the insulin-producing and secreting pancreatic beta-cells become dysfunctional and often die. One of the key players in this process is islet amyloid polypeptide, also known as amylin.

Malfunction and amyloid formation off amylin are contributing factors to type 2 diabetes. In the last few years, scientists have tried to unravel the mechanism of formation and aggregation of amylin and its effect on pancreatic beta-cells. Amylin is a prohormone consisting of a 37-amino acid peptide, co-secreted with insulin by beta-cells in response to high blood glucose levels. Amylin inhibits the gastric emptying and food intake.

In type 2 diabetes, amylin folds and aggregates to form amyloid fibrils which are harmful to the beta-cells.^[49,50] The mis folded amylin is a toxic structure. The aggregation of this structure damages the cell membrane and disrupts the normal cellular function of beta-cells by impairing the ability to produce insulin. This aggregation of misfolded amylin also triggers the inflammatory process within the pancreatic islets which exacerbates the damage of beta-cells.^[51]

This phenomenon reduces the adequate level of insulin production by damaging beta cells and stimulating the disease progression of type 2 diabetes. Researchers are exploring ways to prevent amylin aggregation and neutralize its toxic effects.^[49] But before that, it is important to identify the process of cellular communication of amylin to develop new treatments for type 2 diabetes.

ABSTRACT

Beta-cells produce the two hormones, insulin and IAPP, that regulate blood glucose levels. During the development of type 2 diabetes (T2D), beta-cells are stressed to produce increased amounts of hormones, resulting in dysfunctional cell function and beta-cell death. The hormone IAPP modulates insulin release but is more known for its high propensity to form islet amyloid. Amyloid comprises proteins aggregated

into highly ordered fibrillar structures and deposited in one or more organs. IAPP forms amyloid in almost all individuals with T2D, and the amyloid deposits are present in and around beta-cells and cause beta-cell death.

In the last few years, scientists have tried to unravel the mechanism of formation and aggregation of IAPP and its effect on pancreatic beta-cells.

Studies on IAPP amyloid show that in the beginning, amyloid is present in multiple spots in an islet, and when the amyloid mass grows, all beta-cells will be replaced by IAPP amyloid. This pattern raises the question of whether IAPP amyloid starts at multiple sites or if amyloid formed in one cell can be transferred to an adjacent beta-cell.

In this study, IAPP and IAPP amyloid transfer were studied using co-culture of amyloid-containing human islets and fluorescent acceptor cells, Bimolecular fluorescent complementation (BiFC) was used to produce GFP labelled IAPP/Ab amyloid, and IAPP amyloid formation and spreading was monitored in real-time using a Lumascope.

The expression of fluorescent proteins and immune labelling with specific antibodies were used to identify cell populations, and confocal microscopy was used to determine the transfer of IAPP or amyloid between cells.

In the co-culture of human islet and HEK-293 cells, amyloid could be detected in non-beta cells present in close contact with the amyloid-containing cells. This indicates that amyloid was either transferred between cells or endocytosed by the non-beta-cell. In the BiFC system used, the generation of green fluorescence results from the interaction between the amyloid-forming proteins IAPP and AB. An earlier finding was that IAPP and AB expression results in spot-like amyloid deposits. When HEK293 cells were transfected with ALN2+ILC1 vectors, amyloid was formed, and after co-culture with m-Cherry expressing HEK293 cells, the presence of cells with green and red fluorescence could be found. This points to an interaction between the two populations of HEK 293 cells and the transfer that occurred.

The results support transfer, but further studies that include inhibitors can help to identify the used pathway.

Keywords and Abbreviations:

AA- Amyloid aggregation, APP- Amyloid precursor protein, A β - Amyloid-beta, BSA- Bovine serum albumin
BiFC- Biomolecular fluorescence complementation, DAPI- 4, 6-diamino-2-phenylindole, TEM-
Transmission Electron microscope, GFP- Green Fluorescent Protein, h-FTAA- Heptamer formyl thiophene
acetic acid, IAPP- Islets Amyloid Polypeptide, IA- Islets amyloid, IML- Immunolabelling, IGT-

Impaired glucose tolerance, PMD- Protein Misfolding Disorders, PBSPhosphate-buffered saline, p-FTAA- Pentamer formyl thiophene acetic acid, pro-IAPP- Pro-islets amyloid polypeptide, RPMI- Roswell Park Memorial Institute Medium, RT- Room Temperature, TBS- Tris-buffered saline, TNT- Tunneling nanotubes, T1D- Type 1 Diabetes, T2D- Type 2 Diabetes

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is an endocrine disorder characterized by hyperglycemia due to a relative or absolute lack of insulin secretion. Insulin is a peptide hormone secreted by the beta-cells situated in islets of the Langerhans of the pancreas. Insulin regulates the body's metabolism of fat and carbohydrates. It acts on muscle and fat cells and stimulates the uptake of glucose, lowering the blood sugar level. Diabetes occurs due to a defect in insulin's production, secretion, or action of insulin. There are two main types of diabetes. T1D and T2D. T1D is an autoimmune disorder where complete self-destruction of beta-cells leads to absolute insulin deficiency. The second variant, T2D is characterized by progressive loss of insulin secretion despite having the presence of beta-cells or damage of beta-cells. Genetic predisposition and various environmental factors act together causing the development of diabetes. ^[1] T2D is the most common type of diabetes worldwide, with approximately 530 million adults in 2024 suffering due to T2D. According to a recent report, the global prevalence rate of T2D is approximately 10.5% between the age group 20 years to 79 years. ^[2] The pathogenesis of T2D is comprised of two components: one is peripheral insulin resistance, where muscles and adipose tissue cannot respond to insulin, while the second component is dysfunctional beta-cell. In peripheral insulin resistance, blood glucose levels can be measured to be slightly elevated or normal due to the compensatory mechanism of insulin secretion from beta-cells. This state is known as impaired glucose tolerance (IGT). During the IGT the constant insulin secretion results in a stressful situation which leads to the development of beta-cell dysfunction. ^[3] The stressful situation includes a dramatic increase in hormone production and processing, resulting in the exhaustion of the cells and subsequent beta-cell destruction. In addition to insulin, beta-cells produce a second hormone IAPP, IAPP tends to misfold and form amyloid. IAPP amyloid is known to be cytotoxic and is believed to be the main cause of beta-cell loss in patients with diabetes. ^[4]

Protein Misfolding Disorder

Protein misfolding disorder (PMD) is a pathological condition in which the amino acid sequence or the 3-dimensional structure of protein becomes abnormal and disrupts the physiological function of the protein. PMDs are also known as proteinopathy. ^[9] Proteins are an important chemical building block in all living organisms. The function of a protein is completely dependent on a correct transcription of genetic code and translation of the amino acid sequences. In the very early stage of development, alpha helices and beta sheets of DNA go through a series of conformational changes that maintain biological function throughout life. But sometimes it is very difficult to remain constant in biologically active form due to encountering many challenging tasks in both intracellular and extracellular environments. ^[5] It is believed that a correctly folded protein has adopted its predetermined native

conformation, and this represents the lowest energy state. ^[6]The cell has multiple systems that can remove misfolded proteins or assist in refolding a protein into the correct fold.

In the process of PMD, both proteasomes and chaperones play crucial roles. Together proteasomes and chaperones cause a series of chemical reactions for cellular quality control. Proteasomes are protein complexes known for discarding unnecessary, damaged protein by proteolysis and maintaining cellular homeostasis. Proteasomes identify and break the misfolded proteins by following a series of chemical reactions. ^[52] On the other hand, chaperones are a type of proteins that influence the proper folding of other proteins. Chaperones adequately help newly synthesized proteins too maintain their three-dimensional structure. ^[53] In the case of PMD, the chaperones bind with misfolded proteins and prevent them from aggregating and causing cellular damage by correcting their forms or degrading the misfolded proteins. ^[54,55]

Protein misfolding disease occurs when the protein is unable to fold into its native state or when a correctly folded protein fails to remain in its correct native functional state. ^[7] Protein misfolding is responsible for many different diseases such as sickle cell anemia, an inherited disease where a mutation in the hemoglobin gene give rise to 'sticky' hemoglobin molecules leading to a morphological alteration of the erythrocytes and reducing oxygen transportation. The largest group among the PMDs is amyloidosis and in this group are well-known conditions such as Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, and islets amyloids included. ^[8]

Amyloid and amyloid fibril formation

Amyloids are aggregations of insoluble fibrillar proteins. These amyloids deposit within the extracellular protein and play a role in developing various diseases such as diabetes, systemic amyloidosis, Alzheimer's disease, etc. These diseases are also known as PMD where amyloid acts as a pathogenic structure in the disease mechanism. Pathogenic Amyloid forms when the soluble proteins and peptides start to aggregate abnormally. In most cases, some specific protein and protein domains evolve amyloid fibrils to form quite different structures under certain conditions, for example molecular, cellular, or organismic stress. ^[16]

The physiological function of cells depends on the network formed by the accurate folding of thousands of proteins that contain amino acid sequences. ^[16] A study described that these proteins start to fold when newly synthesized proteins cannot be able to interact with other molecular chaperones which are a variety of cofactors. The function of molecular chaperones is to recognize and interact with the polypeptide chains and intermediate proteins to prevent their aggregation and misfolding. ^[17] A review study has discussed that, the protein misfold usually contains β sheets in a polymeric arrangement and have high tendency to form oligomers and polymers. ^[18] At the same time, aggregation of islet amyloid is a cause of type-2 diabetes though the causative factor of IAPP aggregation is unknown. The aggregation of polymerized IAPP progressively accumulates leading to cell dysfunction and destruction of beta-cells and causing type-2 diabetics. ^[19,20]

Also, many studies showed protein aggregation into the β -strands forms a long structure. It has been shown that many proteins can misfold and form this long structure. These long β -sheet structures stabilize by hydrogen bonds and create straight rigid, and unbranched amyloid fibril. The diameter of amyloid fibrils varies from 5-13nm, and their length can be many micrometres. The fibril structures are the same even though the amyloidogenic proteins differ from one another depending on the amino-acid sequence, native fold, and length. [13]

Figure1: Amyloid Fibril formation where β -sheet are attached with H-bond (Made in biorender.com)

The idea for the initial amyloid formation within the islets states that it starts intracellularly in the secretory granules from inadequately processed proIAPP β -cell. [21] Moreover, in the very early stages of T2D, mature IAPP, processed and partially processed proinsulin, and proIAPP together are located within the cluster of intracellular amyloids and the way of processing is very amyloidogenic which makes them extremely prone to aggregate which can be an initial phase of amyloid formation. [22,23]

Figure2: Aggregation of protein misfolds inside β -cell (Made in biorender.com)

According to another study, the process of amyloid formation is cytotoxic and causes cell apoptosis by which the amyloids are exposed to extracellular space. Later the IAPP secreted from β -cells gathers around the amyloid fibril and forms a large extracellular amyloid mass which is a hallmark of T2D. ^[24]

Another study discussed that it is not always necessary to deposit amyloid within the neighbouring cells though small amyloid deposits are usually spread throughout the entire islets and it is important to note that amyloidogenesis is a nucleation-dependent process which means it only starts when the first amyloid aggregate has formed. Later, the process was subdivided into three stages. In the first stage, nucleation of monomeric peptides is formed. In the second stage, elongation of amyloid fibrils takes place and in the third stage, the fibrillar mass becomes constant. It continues when the fibrillation process is initiated. ^[23,24]

A review study by Ines Moreno-Gonzalez ^[10] proposed a model to describe the mechanism of amyloid formation. The mechanism is separated into three different steps named “lag phase, elongation phase, and plateau phase”. According to this proposed model, seeding nucleation of protein undergo through three phases. First one is lag phase, where a low amount of misfolded and oligomer structures are produced in a slow process generating seeds for the elongation phase. In the elongation phase, the nuclei are formed and cause rapid proliferation leading to the exponential phase. In the exponential phase, the oligomers propagate misfolding in exponential manners. At the same time according to these studies, large structures of fibrils can be a propagating factor due to their higher resistance to biological clearance. ^[10]

Amyloid deposits are most often detected extra cellularly. However, this can depend on that biopsies are from patients that suffer from organ failure most often caused by extensive amyloid deposits and severe tissue damage. Therefore, it is not possible to determine the initial site for amyloid formation. The can be transmitted by an infectious process. At the molecular level, misfolding proteins stimulate the conformational changes within the other native proteins and modify their function by inducing cellular stress and damage. These misfolded proteins transmit from one cell to another and stimulate pathological event throughout the affected cells. Different sub-cellular pathways and cell-cell communication take place in the spreading process, allowing misfolded aggregates to get in contact with native proteins of neighboring cells. These events can happen at both the extracellular and intracellular levels. ^[10]

Islets amyloid polypeptide (IAPP) is a secretory product of β -cells of the pancreatic islets. IAPP is co-released with insulin as a prohormone produced by the 37-amino acid chain. IAPP is synthesized as an 89-amino-acid prepropeptide and edge by two short peptides. Later, the two short peptides are cleaved off to produce basic residues. [11] Biologically active IAPP plays an important role in glucose homeostasis. It also plays a role in satiety regulation and delayed gastric emptying by binding with the specific site in the brain. ^[12] Despite important physiological functions, IAPP is more known for its capacity to form intracellular amyloid aggregates leading to the destruction of beta-cells. Taken together results from multiple studies, inflammation, defective autophagy, stress within the endoplasmic reticulum, formation of free radicals, membrane disruption, and deficient receptor-mediated

mechanism can be responsible for the β -cells destruction. ^[13] Another study shows that incomplete cleavage of Pro-IAPP which is the precursor protein of IAPP also plays a role in developing T2D. The incompletely cleaved Pro-IAPP also co-deposits along with IAPP and triggers the amyloid fibril formation. ^[14] IAPP is a β -cell hormone acting as a modulator of insulin secretion and has been shown to act as a satiety factor. Despite these essential biological functions, IAPP is more known for its ability to form cytotoxic amyloid frequently present in patients with type 2 diabetes. ^[15]

Also, a recent study has shown that IAPP affects cognitive function. In this study they found evidence that IAPP can cross the blood-brain barrier and interact with amyloid β -protein and with tau within the brain in Alzheimer's disease patients and induce diabetes-associated dementia. ^[15]

IAPP expression and function

Islets amyloid polypeptide (IAPP) is a secretory product of β -cells of the pancreatic islets. IAPP is produced as an 89-amino acid long prohormone that undergoes posttranslational processing in the late Golgi and the secretory granules. The processing is pH dependent and includes the removal of N-terminal and C-terminal flanking peptides, C-terminal imitination, and the formation of a disulfate bond between residues 2 and 7 of the IAPP molecule. The processing is executed by the convertases PC2 and PC1/3. These are the same convertases that process proinsulin to insulin at the same cellular compartments. A comparison of the IAPP and insulin genes reveals similarities in the regulatory regions, and both peptides are released from the beta cells upon glucose stimulation. The biologically active peptide is 37 residues long, and signaling occurs through the calcitonin receptor when combined with the receptor activity modifying peptide 1 (RAMP1). IAPP is released together with insulin. Over the years, IAPP has been ascribed to many functions, including an important role in glucose homeostasis, in satiety regulation, and gastric emptying. The two latter functions depend on the binding of IAPP to receptors present within certain specific sites in the brain. ^[12] Despite important physiological functions, IAPP is more known for its capacity to form intracellular amyloid aggregates, leading to the destruction of beta-cells. Taken together, results from multiple studies, inflammation, defective autophagy, stress within the endoplasmic reticulum, formation of free radicals, membrane disruption, and deficient receptor-mediated mechanism can be responsible for the β -cells destruction. ^[13] Another study shows that incomplete cleavage of Pro-IAPP to IAPP plays a role in IAPP amyloid formation and that incompletely cleaved Pro-IAPP also co-deposits along with IAPP. ^[14]

Transmission of amyloid fibrillation:

Amyloidosis can be divided into two groups. Systemic and Local. In systemic amyloidosis, the precursor proteins produced by the liver and plasma cells and circulate in the blood. They polymerize to form amyloid fibrils and deposit around the different tissues throughout the body. In localized amyloidosis, amyloid appears in the organs where the precursor proteins are synthesized, such as the brain, and pancreas. ^[25] A study found evidence of the spreading of amyloid. According to that study, amyloids can spread both in vivo and in vitro and can induce pathological alteration. Amyloids also can cross the blood-brain barrier and can spread from cell to cell. ^[26]

korenaga, et.al experimented the offspring of mice to monitor the transmission of amyloidosis with AApoAII amyloidosis. According to study, pre-existing amyloid fibril can influence furthermore polymerization of endogenous precursor protein and transmission of amyloid fibril AAopAII. They injected the amyloidogenic apolipoprotein A-II gene in mother mice. After 4 months they detected amyloid fibril deposition in the intestine within the newborn which indicates vertical transmission of amyloid fibril through the placenta. ^[27]

Another review study was done by T. Murakami, N. Ishiguro, and k. Higuchi on the transmission of systemic amyloidosis among the animals. They experimented on wild animals. According to the study, amyloid fibrils generate a seeding nucleation process which leads to a conformational change. This event aggravates amyloid deposition around the tissue which causes chronic inflammation and is suspected to spread via the peripheral routes or by oral route. ^[28]

Cell-cell Communication

Cell-cell communication is an important process for all types of cells (both prokaryotes and eukaryotes) by which one cell interacts with intracellular and extracellular substances and other cells. Cell-cell communication is the behavior of one cell influenced by another to coordinate a wide variety of functions to maintain microenvironmental homeostasis. Cell-cell communication can occur in multiple ways. It involves three components: the ligand, the receptor, and the effector. ^[29]

The ligands are mostly chemicals in nature secreted by a cell under some influence such as pressure, voltage, temperature, light, etc. The chemical ligands have the special capability of binding with specific receptors of target cells which can be ions (Na⁺, K⁺, Ca⁺⁺), lipids (steroid, prostaglandin), peptides (Insulin, ACTH), nucleic acid (steroids, thyroid hormones) etc. Target cells can be a neighboring cell or a distant cell. ^[30]

There are different methods of cell-cell communication, such as autocrine, paracrine, and endocrine. Autocrine cell communication is a type of intracellular communication where a ligand secretes from a cell and binds with a specific receptor situated on the same cell to do the desired physiological reaction. In autocrine cell communication, the secreted ligands act on the same cell whereas in paracrine cell-cell communication, the ligands secrete from a cell but bind with a specific receptor of another cell and cause physiological effects. In juxtacrine cell communication depends on gap junctions or other structures such as membrane nanotubes or tunnels to pass ligand molecules directly between the cells without secreting the ligands into extracellular space. But in endocrine cell communication, the ligands secrete into the bloodstream and travel a long way to bind with a specific receptor situated on the membrane of a distant cell. ^[31]

Tunneling nano tube

A tunneling nanotube refers to the versatile cytoskeleton structure from the plasma membrane connecting one cell to another. ^[32] These subcellular structures work as an intracellular bridge between the cells through which cellular materials, pathogens, and electric signals pass from one cell to another. They also play a unique role in different physiological and pathological recovery, such as in embryological cell development, cellular movement, cell recovery from cell injury, etc. ^[33] By the side of physiological and pathological role, many researchers team also

tried to identify possible roles of TNT in drug transportation to the cellular level. According to that researcher's team, TNT could help transport nanomedicine to improve biodistribution throughout a diseased tissue. ^[34]

On the other hand, many data the number of TNT is very minimal in physiologically healthy adult tissues. The number of TNT can be increased due to some pathological stimulation such as, stresses, and inflammatory stimulation, and plays a role in disease transmission. For example: a study has investigated that, TNT plays a major role in the progression of neurodegenerative disease by transferring the prions and other amyloid proteins. ^[35]

Many groups of scientists have discussed the different mechanisms for TNT formation. One group proposed two mechanisms: one is a cytoplasmic protrusion extending from one cell to another, and the other one is that TNT that developed during embryological development remains the same bridge between two previously connected cells. Another group displayed Ca²⁺ flux in response to mechanical stimuli, for example, dendritic cells and monocytes. According to this study, the initial formation speed of TNT is around 35µm/second and connects with monocytes up to 100 µm long. ^[36]

Another group of scientists has proposed two types of TNT such as open-ended and close-ended by studying the ultrastructure using an electron microscope (EM). According to these studies, open-ended TNT is channel-mediated membrane protrusion that makes a connection between two cells. These structures have a diameter between 50-700nm with a length between 20-100µm. These membranous continuities between cells do not derive from cell division. Regarding cytoskeletal composition, it contains actin and microtubules. ^[36,37] In close-ended TNT, a review study states that the close-ended TNT consists of tubulin-containing thick structures such as F-actin filament-like cytoskeletal structure along with both actin and microtubules. According to this review article, in open-ended TNT each end allows cytoplasmic continuity which allows the transfer of intracellular large cargo (e.g., mitochondria, endoplasmic reticulum, ribosomes, etc.) whereas the close-ended TNT facilitates electrical coupling between the cells through the tip of protrusion and allows selective permeability of microstructure. ^[38,39]

Endocytosis

Endocytosis is a process by which external material enters the cells. The cell membrane absorbs or engulfs the material from the external environment. Endocytosed materials can be nutrients, extracellular debris, dead cells, viruses, and bacteria. This process is subdivided into pinocytosis and phagocytosis. In pinocytosis, the cell membrane invaginates the small molecular weight of protein or antigen. ^[40] Depending on the vesicle size pinocytosis is divided into two types and they are macropinocytosis and micropinocytosis. In micropinocytosis, the plasma membrane forms 0.2µm-10µm pinosomes to ingest extracellular fluid. These macropinosomes form after a chaotic movement of the cell cortex or sometimes form acute stimulation of growth factors or other agents. Most of the macromolecules are degraded by acid hydrolase followed by delivering into lysosomes and forming micro molecules. ^[41] On the other hand, micropinocytosis is a worm-like structure first observed in the Kupfer cells of the rat liver. In the beginning, it was thought to be an exaggerated or intensified form of endocytosis. The size of micropinosomes is 80-125nm. ^[42] These vesicles are formed by different endocytic activities such as clathrin-coated vesicles, caveolae, and uncoated vesicles. ^[42,43]

The other process, phagocytosis, involves the ingestion of particles stimulated by exogenous particles that induce actin-dependent cellular extension and wrapping to make an envelope around the particle. After ingestion, the endocytosed particles undergo different procedures, for example, degradation, recycling, or expelling to other destinations. It plays an important role in removing pathogens. [40]

Figure 3: Process of vesicle formation in pinocytosis and the process of pinocytosis. (Made in Bio render)

Figure 4: Process of Phagocytosis. (Made in bio-render)

Exocytosis

Exocytosis is a process by which cells transport material from the cells. In exocytosis vesicles containing cellular debris are transferred to the cell membrane fuse with the cell membrane and release the substances extracellularly. This is an active transport and requires energy. [44]

The size of the vesicles varies in different cell types and the diameters range from 100nm to 1µm. The secretory vesicles develop from the Golgi apparatus and undergo different steps followed by maturation and translocation

towards the plasma membrane. The microtubules play an important role in transporting newly synthesized secretory vehicles from the Golgi apparatus to the cell membrane. [45]

Figure 4: Process of Exocytosis (Made in Bio render)

Trogocytosis

Trogocytosis is a form of cell-cell interaction. With the help of immune cells, this interaction transforms the cell membrane fragments with functional integrity. This transformation also helps to transfer MHC molecules, receptors, antigens, etc. [49]

Trogocytosis is an active process in which one cell transfers cell surface molecules from another cell. Recent reports have shown that trogocytosis plays an important role in biological processes. It also plays a role in innate and adaptive immunity along with in process of cell death followed by antibody-dependent cytotoxicity. [47]

It has suggested that, trogocytosis transfer functional properties from old cell to new cell. It challenges the concept of the process of transferring surface molecules between cells and can also use for therapeutic purposes by indicating monoclonal antibodies. [48]

AIM: The study aims to investigate if IAPP is a monomer aggregated into amyloid that can transfer between cells and, if so, by which mechanism.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Description of Cell line

HEK-293 is a cell line derived from a human embryonic kidney that displays epithelial characteristics. They are well-liked partly due to their consistent culture growth and transfection propensity. The cells are adherent in culture and have a grainy appearance. This line's expression of adenovirus enables cells to continuously generate large amounts of proteins. (<https://www.atcc.org/products/crl-1573>). HEK-293 cells were cultured in RPMI-1640 Medium supplemented with 10% w/w FCS, 100 IU/ml penicillin, 100 µg/ml streptomycin and 45 µM β-mercaptoethanol. Cells were cultured in a humidified chamber in 5% CO₂ at 37°C.

Trypsin treatment

Trypsin was used to detach the cells before sub-culture. These cells were washed with PBS (100mL; pH: 7.4). In place of the 7ml genuine trypsin solution, we used a tenfold diluted version for these. The 10-times trypsin solution was prepared by mixing 0.5 ml of trypsin and 4.5 ml of PBS in a 15 ml tube. Once the trypsin solution is ready, remove the cell culture medium and added the trypsin solution. It was then incubated for 2-5 minutes and used the microscope to confirm that the cell had detached from the surface. Following that, the cells were moved into a 15 ml tube and centrifuged for 5 minutes at 900 RPM. After the centrifuge, a pellet developed, and the supernatant was carefully removed without destroying the pellet. Next, 15 ml of RPMI culture medium was used to solubilize the pellet.

Preparation of vector

To prepare the vector, we followed the steps from the manual supplied with the kits by the company. At first, 600 μ l of opti-mem was mixed with 6 μ g of p-Budmcherry vector (concentration: 673ng/ μ l) and vortexed. Then, 12 μ l of TurboFect was added followed by repeating the vortex and left at room temperature for 20 minutes. For bacterial transformation, 3 μ l of mcherry vector was combined with 50 μ l of 5dHFx bacteria in a snap-lid tube and incubated on ice for 30 minutes, heat-shocked at 42°C, and placed again on ice for 5 minutes. After that, 2ml of LB (Luria Broth) without ampicillin was added, and the mixture was incubated for 60 minutes at 37°C. After that, it was placed on a plate that was incubated at 37°C for the entire night to culture the bacteria. The following day, we took a tinny sample of colonized bacteria mixture that had been combined with LB in a bottle and stored it overnight at 37°C in an indirect heat shake. For plasmid extraction, the 50ml overnight culture was moved to the centrifuge at room temperature for 10 minutes at 4,000xg, and the cells were resuspended in an RNAase A solution. The lysate was clarified solutions II and III and carefully placed in a HiBind® DNA maxi column, ensuring no cellular debris entered. The column was washed multiple times with HBC buffer and DNA wash buffer followed by ethanol washes. The column was then dried and centrifuged to remove the ethanol trace. Finally, the DNA had been extracted with 1.5ml of elution buffer solution and kept at -20°C. Before use, the HiBind® DNA maxi column was equilibrated with 3ml 3mM NaOH, followed by centrifugation and filtration of unwanted products. To check the quality of the newly produced vector, we transfected HEK-293 cells with different concentrations of the newly produced pbudmcherry vector whose concentration was 724ng/ml to test the vector.

Preparation of acceptor cells

HEK-293 cells were selected as an acceptor cell as they do not contain any form of amyloid. At first cells were washed with PBS. Then 1ml of trypsin was mixed with 9ml of PBS and added to the cells and left to incubate for 2 minutes to allow trypsinization. After 2 minutes of incubation, the cells were centrifuged at 900rpm for 5 minutes. The supernatant was removed after centrifugation and a cell mixed with cell culture medium and transferred in two different cell culture flasks. culture medium was added

Preparation of Donor cell

We received pancreatic islets from the Nordic network for clinical islet transplantation from four human donors (2668, 2673, 2679, 2689). Human islets were cultured in two types of CMRL1640 medium in which one contained 5mM of normal glucose and the other one contained 20mM of high glucose. The CMRL1640 (500ml) contains L-glutamate (5ml), FCS (50ml), PEST (5ml).

The isolated human islets with or without amyloid were collected in an Eppendorf tube and semi-digested with trypsin in PBS followed by centrifugation at 300RPM for 3 minutes. Then the supernatant was removed, and the pellet was resuspended in the medium.

BiFC method

Bimolecular fluorescence complementation (BiFC), a technique developed for protein-protein interaction studies, uses the re-establishing of a split fluorophore e.g. green fluorescent protein (GFP). Two different vectors were used, one containing DNA corresponding to the protein of interest followed by the N-terminal fragment of the GFP molecule and vector 2 containing DNA corresponding to the protein of interest followed by the C-terminal fragment of the GFP. When cells were transfected with both vectors, the interaction of the two proteins will pull the N- and C-terminal fragments of GFP together, and a fluorescent molecule can be detected with amicroscope. We transfected HEK293 cells with both or one of the vectors (IN+IC, or IN, or IC).

List of antibodies

Antibody	Origins	Concentration
A133	Anti-IAPP produced in rabbit	1:200
110	Anti-IAPP (Produced in rabbits)	1:200
Alexa 488	Goat anti-rabbit	1:200
Alexa 647	Goat anti-rabbit	1:1000
Alexa 647	Goat anti-mouse	1:1000
CD68 (Monoclonal antibody; clone PG)	Produced in mouse	1:200
CD68 (Monoclonal antibody; Clone KPI)	Produced in mice (different variants)	1:200

Co-culture and immune-staining method

Different co-cultures were set up to find out whether the IAPP amyloid can transfer from the donor cell to the acceptor cells. Cell co-culture is a process by which different types of cells are mixed to see the cellular interaction between the cells. Human islets cultured high glucose medium were used as amyloid-containing cells. The process

of formation of amyloid was monitored by the lumascop 200 for 7 days. As acceptor cells HEK-293 cells were used which were transfected with pbudmcherry. At the same time, HEK-293 cells transfected in BiFC method were co-cultured with islet cells

Co-culture of GFP transfected cells with acceptor cells

From 24 wells plate, we randomly picked cells from 20 wells mixed in a 15ml tube and added 10ml of RPMI medium. Then mixed very well and distributed within the 16 wells of four well plates containing a cover slip from the beginning. Each well-contained 2ml of cell solution and was incubated in a 37°C temperature incubator for 48 hours. Then we collected the BFP transfected cells containing ALN2+ALC1, ILN2+ILC1, ALN2+ILC1, and ALC1+ILN2 in four different 15ml tubes. Then centrifuged 900RPM for 5 minutes followed by removing the supernatant without affecting the palate formed after the centrifugal. Then added 10ml RPMI culture medium and mixed the palate with the medium very well and distributed them within the 16 wells of four well plates where pbudmcherry transfected cells placed. Later more 1.5ml medium containing 200µg/µl zeocin. After 5 days of cultivation of transfected pbudmcherry cells were collected from a Petri dish in a 10ml tube. Mixed 5ml RPMI medium and placed them in 16 wells of four well plates. Then incubated for 48 hours to let the attached with the coverslip placed inside the wells. After 48 hours, we collect BFP containing cells in a 10ml tube and added 5ml of medium and mixed them properly. Then we divided the BFP-containing cell solution on the top of pbudmcherry transfected cells within the 16 wells of four well plates and incubated for four days.

Immunolabeling of BFP transfected cells with acceptor cells

After 4 days expression of both green and red cells where detected by the microscope. Then used 0.1% saponin in TBS to rinse for 5 minutes. Next, the primary antibody 110 produced in rabbit was diluted with TBS-saponin solution at a ratio of 1:200 and added to the cells followed by incubation in 4°C overnight. On the next day, rinse three times in TBS-saponin solution for twenty minutes. Then diluted secondary antibody Alexa 647 was produced in goat at a ratio of 1:1000 in TBS-saponin solution. Then added the primary antibody and incubated for two hours at 4°C. Two hours later, rinsed three times using TBS-saponin solution, for 20 minutes, and then rinsed three times using TBS solution once more. Next, used 1ml of PBS mixed with glycerol mounting solution and 1µl of dapi to mount the cells on slides.

Co-culture of acceptor cells with donor cells

We extracted HEK 293 pBudmcherry transfected cells from a 6-well plate (red fluorescent light detection) which were treated them with 400 µl/ml of zeocin. After trypsinizing the cells, we centrifuged the cell solution for five minutes at 900 RPM. The supernatant was then removed without causing any discomfort to the pellet, and 6ml of culture media was added and thoroughly mixed with the cells. We then plated them into plates with 24 wells. Afterward, these cells were treated with two different concentrations of zeocin (12 wells received 400µg/ml of zeocin, and the remaining 12 wells received 800µg/ml). With the aid of a microscope, it was determined that red

cells were present in the wells treated with 400µg/ml of zeocin, and the wells treated with 800µg/ml of zeocin revealed a very minimal number of transfected cells.

Then we picked transfected HEK-293 cells with 400µg/ml zeocin from four well in a 10ml tube and added 2ml of medium. Then we trypsinized and centrifuged (900 RPM for 5 minutes) the transfected cells. Then removed the supernatant followed by adding 10ml of RPMI culture medium and mixed with the transfected cell palate very well. Later we distributed the cell solution with in the four well plate where a coverslip was placed in each well. We took islet cells from a diabetic patient (donor 2679) and cultivated them for a week in a high-glucose culture. Next, we gathered islet cells and incubated them for five minutes in a 15 ml container. We carefully removed the supernatant whenever the cells sank, added trypsin, and then incubated for three to four minutes. Subsequently, add 10 ml of PBS to the tube, mix it using a pipette, and centrifuge at 800 rpm for 10 minutes. After that, we took out and put 300µl of PBS into each of the three wells of the four-well plates that we had previously used to plate out HEK-293 cells.

Immunolabeling of acceptor cells co-cultured with donor cell

The human islet cells collected from donor 2673 were co-cultured with pbudmcherry transfected HEK-293. After 48 hours of incubation the transfected cells were trypsinized and centrifuged in a 50 ml tube at 900 RPM for 5 minutes. The supernatant were removed very carefully and the palate was subsequently mixed with 10ml culture medium was added, and divided in a four-well plate. Later the islet cells were collected in an Eppendorf tube with 1ml of PBS and left for 5min. In 5 minutes the islets went down forming a soft palate at the bottom of the tube. Then removed the supernatant very carefully and added two times diluted trypsin followed by incubation for 3 minutes. Then mixed the palate by pipetting up and down. Then filled the tube with 10ml PBS and centrifuged in 300RPM for 3 minutes. Then supernatant was removed and added 3ml of PBS. After that the cells were mixed and distributed in the 3 wells among the four well plate where a cover slip was placed earlier.

After a few days, rinsed the co-cultured islets cells with Hek-293 pBudmcherry cells 0.1% saponin in TBS. Subsequently, diluted primary antibody 110 produced in mouse in 1:200 TBS-saponin solution was added and left it for the entire night in 4°C. The following day rinsed three times in TBS-saponin solution for twenty minutes. On next day, the cells were rinsed three times with 0.1% saponin in TBS for twenty minutes. Then added the secondary antibody Alexa 647 which is goat antirabbit was diluted at a ratio of 1:1000 and incubated for two hour. Rinsed three times with TBS-saponin solution two hours later for 20 minutes. After 20 minutes, rinse three times with TBS solution again. After that, mount the cells on slides using 1 ml of PBS combined with 1µl of dapi and glycerol mounting solution.

Co-culture of Human Islets cells with α -tc cells

After being cultivated in 100µl of culture medium, α -tc cells were plated out into two four-well plates where a cover slip was attached and allowed to sit for an hour. After being cultivated in two distinct glucose-containing CLRM media, islet cells were introduced along with the α -tc cells.

After gathering the cells, we fixed them for 40 minutes in 4% paraformaldehyde in room temperature. After rinsing with TBS with 0.1% triton for ten minutes, the sample was incubated with 0.3% triton for thirty minutes in room temperature. The primary antibody Alexa 647, an anti-glucagon generated in rabbits at a dose of 1:1000, was then added, and it was incubated for four hours at 4°C. After that, another primary antibody, 133, which is anti-IAPP produced in rabbits, was added at concentration 1:200, and it was left to sit for the entire night at 4°C.

On the following day, rinsed the cells three times for ten minutes with 0.1% triton. Subsequent antibody Alexa 647, produced in goat and it is an anti-rabbit, was then added at a concentration of 1:1000 and left for two hours in 4°C temperature. After that, placed the cells on slides using 1 ml of PBS combined with glycerol mounting medium and 1µl of dapi.

Immunolabelling of Co-culture of Human Islets cells with HEK-293 cells

Human islet cells (Donnor 2668) cultured in 20µg/ml high glucose in CMRL1066 culture media for five days. The cells placed in a Lumascope 620 incubator follow the formation of amyloid. Next, the human islet cells were co-cultured with HEK-293. The cells were trypsinized and centrifuged in a 50 ml tube at 900 RPM for 5 minutes. The supernatant was removed very carefully and the palate was subsequently mixed with 50ml of culture medium, of which 5ml was transferred to a large flask, 10ml was added, and the remaining solution was divided in a four-well plate. Later the islet cells were collected in a 15ml tube with 1ml of PBS and left for 5min. In 5 minutes the islets went down forming a soft palate at the bottom of the tube. Then removed the supernatant very carefully and added two times diluted trypsin followed by incubation for 3 minutes. Then mixed the palate by pipetting up and down. Then filled the tube with 10ml PBS and centrifuged in 800RPM for 10 minutes. Then supernatant were removed and added 3ml of PBS. After that the cells were mixed and distributed in the 3 wells among the four well plate where a cover slip was placed earlier. For forty minutes, co-cultured cells were preserved in 4% paraformaldehyde. Next, for ten minutes, washed three times with TBS mixed with 0.1% triton followed by a 30-minute TBS incubation period with 0.3% triton X-100. Primary antibodies against TTR and CD68 which has two subtype KPI and PG were added. Both primary antibody anti-TTR and CD68 are monoclonal antibodies and were produced in mice. 2ml of Anti-TTR was added to one baker, along with triton X 100, to achieve a final concentration of 0.1%. Subsequently, 10µl of KPI and PG varieties of CD68 antibody with 0.1% triton was added to another baker. The two subtypes of CD68 antibodies were added once more to the other baker; KPI and PG were added in 10µl and anti-IAPP were added in 5µl, resulting in a final concentration of anti-IAPP of 1:400. Then the islets mixed with primary antibodies were incubated overnight at 4°C.

On the following day, the islets were rinsed with 0.1% triton for 10 minutes total of 6 times. to detect reactivity with secondary antibodies use two different types of antibodies. Antibodies produced in rabbits are incubated with goat-anti rabbit labelled with Alexa 488. Antibodies produced in mouse is incubated with goat-anti mouse labelled with Alexa 647. To reach the concentration of 1:1000, 4ml of triton 0.1% solution and 4µl of Alexa 647 were combined

in a baker. Simultaneously, in a separate mixer, 4 ml of 0.1% triton was combined with 4 μ l of both Alexa 647 and Alexa 488, with a desired concentration of 1:1000 for each antibody. Then both secondary antibodies were diluted 1:1000 in TBS with triton 0.1% triton X-100 incubated at room temperature for 120 minutes. After islet cells were collected, they were placed on slides along with 1 ml of mounting solution, 50% PBS, and 1 μ l of dapi.

RESULT

Characterization of the newly isolated vector

HEK-293 cells in 4-well plates were transfected with 1,2,4 and 8 μ g/ml cell culture medium of the newly produced pbudmcherry vector and cultured for 24 and 48 hours before inspection of cells to confirm the presence of red, fluorescent cells. In wells with cells transfected with 1 μ g vector (Figure 6A), only a few red cells could be detected while an increased number of red cells appeared after transfection with 2-8 μ g (Figure B-D). No obvious difference in the number of transfected cells could be detected. Since transfection is harmful to cells. So, the concentration of 2 μ g vector/ml was selected for future transfection.

Figure 6: The presence of red fluorescence in HEK-293 cells after transfection with different concentrations of the pBudmcherry vector. A) Red cells are present, but the number is low. B-D) An increased number of red cells are present.

Preparation of acceptor cell

The pbudmcherry vector carries zeocin resistance and untransfected cells will die in the presence of zeocin. A pilot experiment was performed to determine the optimal zeocin concentration. In the stock solution, the zeocin concentration was 100mg/ml, and 100, 300, 400, and 600 μ g/ml of zeocin were added to the cell culture medium. Cells were cultured for 48 hours and the ratio of transfected and untransfected cells was determined. The concentrations of 100 and 300 had low effects while 600 μ g/ ml was toxic to the cells, Therefore the concentration of 400 μ g/ ml of zeocin was selected for future transfected cell culture medium.

Figure 7: HEK-293 cells were cultured in 6-well plates and cultured in 4ml medium. When transfected, the medium was replaced with 2ml with 2 μ g vector/ml medium. For the generation of stable transfected cells, 400 μ g zeocin/ml cell culture medium was added. Cells were cultured for 8 days and repeatedly inspected for red fluorescence to ensure that transfected cells are survived.

Preparation of donor cell

The isolated human islets with or without amyloid were collected in an Eppendorf tube and semi-digested with trypsin with PBS followed by centrifugation 300RPM for 3 minutes. Then the supernatant was removed, and the palate was resuspended in the medium containing normal glucose and high glucose respectively. Human islet cells were grown in 20 μ g/ml high glucose in CMRL1640 culture media for 7 days. Then the islets were stained with 30 μ M p-FTAA before placing them in the incubator. The cells were housed in a Lumascop 620 incubator for 7 days. The figure demonstrates the structure stained with p-FTAA developed in human islets cultured in high glucose for 7 days. The stained area increases during the culture of high glucose.

Figure 8: Islets amyloid formation over 14 days after staining with p-FTAA. The staining is visible in all panels (1-6) demonstrating the progressive formation and deposition of amyloid in the human islet cells over the 14-day culture period in a high-glucose environment. This indicates a significant accumulation of amyloid fibril. These results also indicate the culturing of human islets in high glucose concentrations (20mM) aggravates the amyloidogenic process. The progressive rise of p-FTAA staining over time significant accumulation of which is a pathogenic hallmark of diabetes.

Biomolecular Fluorescence Complementation (BiFC)

At first cultured ALN2, ALC1, ILN2, and ILC1 individually with HEK-293. At the same time used double combination of ALN2+ILC1, and ALC1+ILN2 to culture HEK-293 as a control to detect green fluorescence because of recombination of the GFP. The cells transfected with a single vector were cultured in a medium mixed with zeocin to reduce the number of untransfected cells. Then we trypsinized the cells and mixed them with ALN2+ALC1, ILN2+ILC1, ALN2+ILC1, and ALC1+ILN2. We cultured for 7 days in a medium with zeocin and inspected the cells for the appearance of a GFP signal. After multiple trials, we did not detect any GFP signal and interpreted it as no transfer occurred.

Figure 9: This figure demonstrates the positive control of transfection following the method BiFC of HEK-293 cell. (A-B) is demonstrating the positive HEK-293 cells with ILN2 & ILC1 (A good number of green, fluorescent cells were detected). (C-D) shows positive HEK-293 cells with ALC1 & ALN2 (a very small number of green, fluorescent cells were detected by microscope)

Co-culture of GFP transfected cells with acceptor cells

The HEK-293 cells were co-cultured with the combination of ALN2+ALC1, ILN2+ILC1, ALN2+ILC1, and ALC1+ILN2 respectively, and confirmed the presence of green signal as a confirmation of the establishment of GFP. Then the cells were added to the wells where the acceptor cells (HEK 293 transfected with pbdmcherry) already had been placed.

Figure 10: Biomolecular Fluorescence Complementation (BiFC) pBudmcherry transfected HEK-293 cells and ALN2+ALC1 transfected HEK-293 cells were co-cultured for 48 hours. Cells transfected with BiFC emit green fluorescence, and the cells transfected with pBudmcherry emit red fluorescence. If transfer occurs during co-culture, cells with red and green fluorescence are expected to occur. Cells with overlapping fluorescence suggest cell-cell transfer between the acceptor cell and donor cell.

Figure 11: Confocal image of co-cultured pBudmcherry transfected HEK-293 cells with ALN2+ALC1 transfected cells after 2 days. A. Demonstrating the cells transfected with pBudmcherry. B. Showing the cells transfected with amyloids responsible for Alzheimer's disease. C. Both types of co-cultured cells merged.

Figure 12: Co-cultured pbudmcherry transfected HEK-293 cells with ILN2+ILC1 transfected cells after 2 days of co-culture. This area demonstrates that the two cell types are clustering together, possibly interacting through mechanisms like cell adhesion or other forms of cellular communication.

Figure 13: Confocal image of co-cultured Pbudmcherry transfected HEK-293 cells with ILN2+ILC1 transfected cells after 2 days. A. Demonstrating the cells transfected with pbudmcherry. B. Showing the cells transfected with amyloids responsible for Islets amyloid polypeptide. C. Both types of co-cultured cells merged.

Here an interaction between homologous bi-fluorescence protein and a potential expression toxicity within the living cells. The IAPP entered the cell which is visible as a green signal within the cells.

Immunolabeling of GFP transfected cells with acceptor cells

The immunolabelling procedure was done to detect GFP protein expression and its interaction with acceptor cells (pbudmcherry transfected HEK-293 cells). The detection of both green and red fluorescence suggests evidence of proper transfection. The use of primary antibody 110 (produced in rabbits) targeted specific proteins and bound with the secondary antibody Alexa 647 (Goat anti-rabbit) allowing the detection of red fluorescence. The 0.1% saponin in TBS permeabilizes the cell membrane and facilitates the antibodies to enter the cell which is very important to detect localized protein inside the cell rather than on the cell surface. Dapi is useful to identify the cell nuclei in blue color and helps to distinguish between the nuclear and cytoplasmic region of the cell.

Figure 14: This figure demonstrates immunostaining of ILC1, anti-IAPP, and Alexa 647. The cells are primarily showing green fluorescence associated with ILC1. A-C indicates the cells are expressing GFP which was done by the BiFC method. A) suggesting no significant red fluorescence which might not be detectable under this condition or lack of IAPP expression. B) Showing a mixture of green and very little red fluorescence suggesting a co-localization of both ILC1 and IAPP. The overlapping situation of both green and red might indicate the presence of these proteins in both types of cells. C) mostly green with no significant red fluorescence which might be due to lack of IAPP.

Figure 15: This figure demonstrates immunostaining of ILN2, anti-IAPP, and Alexa 647. A) Predominant green fluorescence suggests ILN2. B) A few areas with both green and red fluorescent expressing both ILN2 and the presence of IAPP are less prominent. C) primarily shows green fluorescence with very few red fluorescence which suggests ILN2 is the dominant protein where IAPP is hardly detectable.

Co-culture of acceptor cells with donor cells

We extracted pbudmcherry transfected HEK-293 cells and co-cultured them with p-FTAA stained amyloid-containing islets cells. We selected the wells mixed with very minimal concentrated zeocin (400µg/ml) as the number of red fluorescence cells was higher than the wells where zeocin concentration was higher (800µg/ml). After

4 days of co-culture between donor cells and acceptor cells we observe the cells under the microscope. During these 4 days, the cell culture medium was carefully replaced.

Figure16: confocal microscope images of A. IAPP formation within the islet cells after culture in high glucose. B. pBudmcherry transfected cells co-cultured the islet cells. C. pBudmcherry transfected cells which are embedded together within the islet cells. These suggests an interaction between amyloid-containing human islets and mcherry-transfected HEK-293 cells. The overlap between the fluorescence signals in the merged image gives an impression of cell-cell transfer of amyloid which leads to the idea that amyloid can transfer between cells.

Immunolabeling of acceptor cells co-cultured with donor cell

Islets from donor 2673 were co-cultured with pBudmcherry expressing HEK-293 cells.

The HEK-293 was cultured on 13 mm coverslips in four-well plates and the semi-digested islets were added to acceptor cells. Co-culture continued for 4 days, and during this period, the cell culture medium was carefully replaced so as not to affect the cells. At the end of the co-culture, cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde, and an immunolabelling procedure was done to detect the specific protein and cellular interaction. The primary antibody 110 the protein and the secondary antibody Alexa 647 emit the fluorescence signal indicating the localization of the target protein. With the overlapping of both green and blue fluorescence, the pathogenic amyloid protein may be transferred from the donor cell to the acceptor cell. The dapi stain the cell nuclei indicates the area of the nuclear and cytoplasmic regions.

Figure17: Confocal microscopic image of Immunolabeling of the co-cultured transfected cells with amyloid-containing islets cells. The green fluorescence (A) represents the presence of amyloid detected by the primary antibody which is effectively bound to its target. This indicates the target antigen amyloid is formed within the co-cultured cells. The blue fluorescence (B) shows Dapi staining, specifically highlighting the nuclei. In the merged image(C) combined with green (Alexa 647) and blue dapi fluorescence signals indicating the amyloid is associated with a specific cellular structure.

Co-culture and of Human Islets cells with α -tc cells

The α -tc cells were co-cultured with islet cells in two different concentrations of glucose environment (20 mM & 5 mM). The cells were fixed by using 4% paraformaldehyde. Then used triton to stimulate cellular permeability to allow antibodies to enter inside the cell. The first primary antibody Alexa 647 (anti-glucagon) used to track the glucagon produced by α -cell. The another primary antibody A133 (anti-IAPP) used to detect the IAPP co-secreted with insulin from beta-cells and associated with pathogenic amyloid formation.

Figure 18: This image showing the transfected HEK-293 cells co-cultured with human islet cells, demonstrating the co-localization of amyloid in transfected HEK-293 cells. In picture A, the presence of green fluorescence indicates

the amyloid transfer took place from islet cells to HEK-293 cells. In picture B, the overlapping of both green and blue suggest that, amyloid containing donor cells may be transferred to the acceptor cells.

Figure 19: This image demonstrates the co-localization of amyloid in transfected HEK-293 cells. The green fluorescence (A) indicated the presence of amyloid, while the blue signal (B) represents nuclear staining of DAPI. The overlapping image (C) suggests differential expression of glucagon (detected by Alexa 647) and IAPP in alpha-tc-6 cells cultured in high concentration of glucose and this also indicates strong IAPP staining. This data indicates that high glucose levels aggravate amyloid formation and these amyloids can be taken up by the acceptor cells.

Immunolabelling of Co-culture of Human Islets cells with HEK-293 cells

Islets cultured in high glucose (20 mM) for 5 days potentially induce amyloid formation. The islets cultured in high glucose were co-cultured with HEK 293 followed by trypsinization, centrifugation and lastly distributed in a 4-well plate. After 4 days of co-culture, the cells were fixed by using 4% paraformaldehyde, and at the same time Triton was used to stimulate permeability of the cell membrane so that the antibodies could enter the cells. The first primary antibody anti-TTR was used to identify the misfolded protein. The second primary antibody anti-CD68 has two subtypes: KPI and PG subtype. This anti-CD68 targets the macrophage and indicates the immune response against amyloid formation. The distinction between the two subtypes was used to identify different macrophage activation states which were not properly detected. Another primary antibody anti-IAPP detects IAPP. The first secondary antibody Alexa 488 is a goat-anti-rabbit and emits green fluorescence and indicates cellular stress due to potential misfolding of protein. Another secondary antibody Alexa 647 is a goat-anti-mouse that emits red fluorescence.

Figure 20: HEK 293 with high glucose islets CD68 and Alexa 647. The presence of purple fluorescence represents the TTR and possibly involved in amyloid formation in the islets. The blue fluorescence represents the dapi staining indicating the presence of the nucleus of the cells giving an impression about the presence of TTR and CD68 with specific cells. The overlapping of purple and blue fluorescence indicates the amyloidogenic process might be associated with the cellular nuclear region or surrounding cytoplasm. The interaction between the HEK-293 cells and human islets cells with a focus on amyloid formation is crucial for the pathogenesis of disease with amyloidosis.

Figure 18: HEK 293+ anti-glucagon+alexa 647. The anti-glucagon antibody specifically binds to glucagon. The red fluorescence suggests the presence of glucagon within the cells. The co-localization of glucagon within the islets the presence of glucagon secreting alpha-cells within the islets.

Figure 22: Hek 293 islets in high glucagon CD68 + Alexa 488. Green fluorescence is associated with activated macrophage, indicating potential immune cell activity. The green fluorescence indicates the presence of IAPP associated with amyloid formation leading to the extent of amyloid deposition.

DISCUSSION

This study aims to investigate the possible mechanism behind the cell-cell transfer of amyloid, focusing on IAPP in the context of human Islets. The process of amyloid transfer between the cells is an important area of study, especially in the context of PMD such as T2D, where amyloid aggregation in pancreatic islets causes mass destruction of beta-cells following the process of apoptosis. To identify the process, we approached multiple methods for example, it involves both co-culture and transfection techniques, combined with advanced imaging and fluorescence detection methods. This broad technique provides a complete framework for investigating the possible mechanism of amyloid transfer between the cells.

Transfection and Staining Efficiency

The co-culture of HEK-293 cells transfected with ALN2+ALC1 and pBudmCherry. The appearance of cells with two fluorophores suggests that material was transferred between cells. It is impossible to determine if the material was transferred from the HEK-293 cell transfected with pBudmCherry to HEK-293 cells transfected with ALN2+ALC1 or vice versa. The used BiFC constructs have been described in detail. One novel finding was that co-

expression of ALN2+ALC1, ALN2+ILC1, or ILN2+ALC1 resulted in a spot-like green fluorescence. Further analysis of these spots with Congo red and transmission electron microscopy reveals that the green spot was amyloid composed of AB or a mixture of AB and IAPP^[5]. Amyloid is known to interact with cell membranes, and therefore, it is probable that the transfer is from the LN2+LC1 transfected cells to the pBudmCherry-expressing cells.

Furthermore, the presence of green fluorescence in Figures 9 and 10 indicates the co-expression of proteins ILC1, ILN2, ALC1, and ALN2 potentially through the following the steps of BiFC technique. The BiFC method is a powerful tool for confirming protein-protein interaction and amyloid transfer between the cells. The split of the EYFP system, reconstitute fluorescence during IAPP from different cells interacts and provides direct evidence of amyloid transfer.

While the BiFC method is highly specific, but still we faced some limitations. The most important issue is the sensitivity of the assay to detect low levels of interaction which can be false negative. Moreover, the fluorescence signal depends on the proper folding and assembly of EYFP, which can be influenced by cellular conditions or the presence of other interacting proteins or foreign particles. So, ensuring the proper BiFC signal is crucial for the correct interpretation of the result.

Islets are very packed and dense structures. Therefore, there are a lot of materials inside the islets which can scatter the light. During the confocal imaging, the penetrating laser light was scattered by highly dense structures during passing throughout the islets leading to a low quality of images.

When talking about a specific antibody binding, the monoclonal antibodies anti-rat/mouse used during the co-culture experiment are only specific for mouse proinsulin. Because the antibodies specifically bind only to the processing site to proinsulin, during the time of producing insulin from proinsulin. The later process solely takes place in late Golgi and immature secretory granules. The antibody against insulin is less specific because the antibody can bind any site on proinsulin peptide during the processing time.

(Figures 6-9) detail the transfection of HEK-293 with different vectors including pbudmcherry and the application of zeocin to create a stable cell line demonstrating efficacy in transfection by emitting red fluorescence. Over the period the increased number of mcherry expressing red fluorescence suggests a successful transfection and selection process.

In the co-culture technique, amyloid-containing donor cells were cultured with amyloid-deficient acceptor cells, which led to tracking amyloid transfer between two different types of cells. Using p-FTAA labeled amyloid, the transfer was visualized and quantified using a fluorescence microscope. The fluorescence labelling with p-FTAA allowed the monitoring of the real-time amyloid transfer as green specks within co-culturing semi-digested, amyloid-labeled human islets with mcherry-expressing acceptor cells. This method demonstrated amyloid transfer attributing multiple potential mechanisms for cell-cell transfer. The mechanisms of cell-cell transfer could be TNT, exocytosis, endocytosis, or trogocytosis.

Amyloid Formation and Cellular Interaction

(Figures 8,16,17,19,20) explore the formation and deposition of amyloid, which is a hallmark of amyloidogenic diseases like T2D, and Alzheimer's disease. The progressive accumulation of amyloid is indicated by p-FTAA staining focused on the pathogenic process aggravated by high concentrations of glucose. This finding correlates with the hypothesis that high glucose stimulates amyloid formation and leads to islet dysfunction.

This method allows continuous observation of amyloid transfer between the cells. The use of two different fluorescent markers (pFTAA for amyloid and pbudmcherry for acceptor cells) ensures the detection of amyloid transfer. However, the limitation faced during the approach was the potentiality for false positives due to the overlap of the fluorescence signal. The image delivered the visual evidence of transfer, but it was challenging to determine the exact underlying mechanism. Strict control and additional measures might be needed to ensure the accuracy of the observation.

Infrequently, some external materials such as threads from textiles had internalized into the islets, giving a green signal with p-FTAA staining. Most of the time, these foreign particles were misleading as amyloid deposition resulting in misinterpretation of the p-FTAA-stained area.

Another challenge during amyloid counting was the auto-fluorescent structures of other cellular organelles in the islet's cell. Very frequently, these cells were seen in the periphery of the islets leading to increased autofluorescence, which should not be considered as amyloid. The problem was tried to minimize by increasing the threshold to make it invisible during amyloid counting with the image. Unfortunately, in some cases, it was not enough to deal with the problem of auto fluorescence.

(Figures 16, 17, and 20) emphasize the cellular interaction between donor cells (amyloid-containing islets) and acceptor cells (amyloid deficient cells; HEK-293 transfected with pbudmcherry). The co-localization of both green and red fluorescence (both amyloid protein and transfected cells respectively) together suggests the aggregated amyloid formed inside the islets has transferred to transfected HEK-293 cells. This is an important finding that implies that aggregated amyloid protein can transfer from one cell to another, potentially giving an idea of cellular spreading pathogens. The observation of overlapping two fluorescence signals gives an idea about the possibility of intercellular communication facilitating the spread of pathogenic amyloids.

Immune Response and Amyloid Accumulation

(Figures 20 and 22) are highlighting the potential immune response associated with amyloid formation. In Figure 22, the green fluorescence denotes the activated macrophages suggesting the immune system might be reacting to amyloid deposition within the islets. This phenomenon gives an idea about the process of how immune systems try to mitigate amyloid-related cellular damage in the tissues.

These findings have significant implications for understanding the pathogenesis of amyloidogenic diseases. The co-culture experiments and evidence of amyloid transfer between the cells suggest a potential mechanism of aggregation of amyloid fibrils within the cells and destructing the beta-cells.

CONCLUSION

The study aims to identify interactions between pathogenic amyloid-forming proteins and human cells particularly in the context of T2D. The transfer of p-FTAA-stained amyloid from the donor cell to the acceptor cell supports the primary hypothesis about the possibility of intercellular transfer of pathogenic amyloid. However, the mechanism of intercellular interactions of amyloid was not identified.

The most attention and effort were paid to tracking the amyloid transfer from a human donor cell into the pbdmcherry transfected HEK-293. It was found that monoclonal antibodies anti-rat/mousesuccessfully stain human IAPP in co-culture samples. These allowed for amyloid seeding to be investigated by exploiting the potential of confocal and electron microscopes. However, during this study, the fusion area between the donor and acceptor cells was not located; therefore, further investigation is needed.

The progressive accumulation of amyloid in human islet cells in high-concentration glucose proves the role of hyperglycemia in exacerbating the amyloidogenic process. This finding describes the pathway of amyloid deposition in pancreatic islets leading to beta-cells dysfunction, and disease progression.

The results also suggest a potential role of the immune system in response to amyloid deposition which is supported by the presence of activated macrophages in **(Figure 22)**. This result can be applied to develop therapeutic strategies targeting the immune response to amyloid deposition.

Overall, these experiments provide a piece of evidence for the interplay between amyloid formation, cellular interactions, and disease processes. The amyloid formation in a high glucose environment and the ability of amyloid to cell transfer between the cells highlights the scope for future research. These findings could lead to develop novel therapeutic approaches to prevent amyloid-related diseases such as T2D, and Alzheimer's disease.

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